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Cultural Value And Student Sex Life In Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the influence of cultural values on the sexual behavior and attitudes of students in secondary schools. Cultural norms and beliefs play a significant role in shaping young people's understanding of sexuality, gender, roles, and acceptable conduct. In many societies, traditional values emphasize abstinence, modesty, and moral discipline, while modern influence and media exposure often present more liberal view on sex. This tension between traditional and contemporary values create a complex environment for adolescents, who are at formative stage or personal development. The finding reveals a significant gap between cultural prescriptions and actual behavior, highlighting the need for culturally sensitive sex education programmers that respect local values while addressing the realities of adolescent sexual behavior. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the cultural dynamics affecting student's sexual health and development in secondary school settings.

Keywords: Cultural values, Student, Sex life, Secondary school, Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

The word culture is synonymous with civilization. This is because culture debits everything that human learned and live for in their entire life time. It is a complex pattern of living that human developed and passes on from one generation to the other. As a human creation culture is strictly a product of human society, their distinctive way of life because different cultures end conflicts between societies arise from cultural differences. Therefore, cultural value are those collective conceptions of what is considered goods, desirable, acceptable, proper and improper in a culture. They indicate what people in a given culture prefer as well as what they find important and morally right or wrong – Richard (2009).

However, value influences people's behavior and serve as criteria for evaluating the actions of others. The value, norms and sanctions of a culture are often directly related. E.g. if a culture places a value on the institution of marriage, it may have norms with strict sanctions that prohibit the act of adultery. This same value runs when you look at the moral value of persons in the society when a child is growing up from age 10 and above.

The value they learnt during their training period and their contact with peers, builds a different thought wave in them. There characters keep changing over time and if not on check could result to a disaster. Considerably, the process of their upbringing parental control, close watch mechanism, sanctions will give what may be accepted by the society. Bhatia (1986) in Ogbonnay (2009) noted five value behavior in a child.

1. ability to apply moral principles to situation.
2. learning values, rules and its application.
3. learning motives, attitudes from people who are nearer to them.

4. formation of ideas/self at age 5 to 6.
5. to learn forming scale of values within self.

Unfortunately, most students in secondary schools have swiftly thrown away their moral values and control over immoral attitudes like sexuality in school. Their honesty, family value, integrity according to Ogbonnaya (2009) have suddenly belong dignified in the schools to the ridicule of the school administrators and the entire country. This immoral attitudes crept slowly in secondary schools through social media exposures, peers group influence and poverty. Poverty is the sense that most students train themselves in school. They endue in so many things to survive in life, so much that those good ones among them in school are lured to doing same thing. It is becoming fashional among the teenagers in secondary schools.

Sex hawking has gradually become rampant among them in school, mostly those living in boarding house and those that exhibit their nakedness on social media platforms. For most of them, it is normal business aimed at sourcing money to pay fees and maintain their self, some even send proceed to their parents at home. It is through this process that they also endue in hard drugs. Cardoso (2003) pointed that any financial profit gotten in ill manner such as this, is completely unacceptable.

The corrupt system of our country Nigeria is not left out in the share of the blame. They contribute to what we see now as student prostitution in schools. The government has failed its citizens by destroying the economy and the school system where every individual is left to their fate. The sexual appetites of this children should be drastically put in control by constant check and stiff discipline in schools and strong sanction in most of the website during school time. Their school uniforms should be modeled in such a way that it will not bring out their shapes or expose their body completely. Schools should activate their counseling unit in such a way that ones in a week, students will be subjected to a kind of panel for proper fellowship.

Statement of the Problem

The performance of secondary school student, their attitude towards sex and immoral behaviours at school and home is very annoying. Unwanted pregnancy, high rate of school dropout because of early pregnancy is so disturbing that if care is not taken, our society will be littered with criminals. The number of secondary school student holding android phones of very high value and their number in different website, social groups, sex site and registered sex hawk groups motivated the researcher to this work.

School administrators are the organized set of people whose responsibility it is to control the excesses in school compounds and monitor behaviour and attitude of students for better placement. But their loose attitude and government irresponsibility to provide for her citizens, brought the students to resort to prostitution in school at a tender age of 14 and 15 years.

Objective of the Study

7. The purpose of this study is to examine what behaviours of students in secondary schools are seen as immoral
8. To examine the best counseling strategy that will increase students morality in secondary schools.

Research Questions

- iii. What is the measurement of students attitude and behaviour that will be commonly seen as immoral?
- iv. What counseling strategy should be used to increase students morality in secondary school?

Hypothesis

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of teachers and students on the strategies to increase student's morality in secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, descriptive survey design was adopted as structured questionnaire developed was used as an instrument for data collection. And it was validated by an expert in measurement and evaluation department, where 450 students, 150 secondary school teachers were drawn from three secondary schools in the sensational zones of Rivers State. The first table is made up of 6 items which includes students and teachers behaviour and attitude commonly seen as immoral while the 2nd table contain 10 items which investigate the opinion of the respondent on counseling strategy used to increase student

morality in school. A four points modified Likert scale weighted 4,3,2,1 for strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly is agreed (SA). The reliability estimate ranged from 0.74 – 0.81 was tested.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the measurement of student’s attitude and behaviour that will be commonly seen as immoral?*

Table 1: Mean response of students and teachers on behaviours and attitudes commonly seen as immoral.

S/NO	ITEMS	TEACHERS	STUDENT
1.	Pornographic viewing	3.50	3.65
2.	Sex hawking	3.95	3.99
3.	Having sex with teachers/students	3.85	3.55
4.	Drug abuse	3.85	3.21
5.	Indecent dressing	3.50	3.22
6.	Kissing opposite sex during school hours	3.25	2.95

Table 1 indicates that teachers and students had mean scores greater than 2.50 in 6 items its schools equal rating on teacher/student behaviour and attitude commonly seen as immoral act.

Research Question 2: *What counseling strategy should be used to increase student’s morality in secondary school?*

Table 2. Mean response of teachers and students on what counseling strategy should be used to increase students’ morality in secondary schools.

S/NO	ITEMS	TEACHERS	STUDENT
1.	Teachers & Administrators to show good examples in school	3.21	3.5
2.	Students to dress decently	3.51	3.62
3.	Students should be loved and accepted unconditionally/equal	2.53	3.61
4.	Schools to promote enlightenment programs in schools to promote moral education.	2.80	2.55
5.	Making contact with parents	3.01	2.05
6.	Rewarding good behaviour in school	3.25	3.26
7.	Parents & Teachers should not dictate students career courses		
8.	Encourage students to have self esteem	3.08	3.69
9.	Parents & Teachers should send time with their children or student	3.32	3.72
10.	Teachers should promote sporting activities in school	3.43	3.82

The 10 item in table 2 above indicate that teacher and students had mean scares greater than 2.5 in the whole. That is balance in the rating rejected by the teachers & students.

DISCUSSION

Table 1: as seen above clearly shows that immoral acts exist in secondary schools, it expresses the knowledge of both teachers and students on the why and how of those immoral acts that had eaten up the school. The finding shows that teachers and student jointly accept the fact in the items as against a better moral living.

Table 2: also indicated that teachers and students had mean scores greater than the scale mean of 2.5 in the 6 items. While the students score below the scale indicating that the mean of 2.5 in item 5 which indicate that students are against teachers making contact with their parents when they go wrong or notice them exhibit an immoral act in school. This shows that students already known that their behaviour is wrong and need to be corrected in schools without contacting their parents at home.

Other items indicate caution in the part of the teachers who take advantage of their pupils. Rewarding good behaviour is a pointer to other students who will lie to emulate the reward mechanism adopted by the school.

According to Johnson (2023) in a rural town in Rivers State, about 45% of in-school adolescents reported initiating sexual activity. Intriguingly, the average age of sexual debut was just around 12 years, with some cases starting as early as 5 years. A majority of these youths had multiple sexual partners, though there was also a relatively high awareness of contraception with condoms being the most recognized and used method.

In another study by Okoro (2022) reported that Port Harcourt context found a lower prevalence of sexual activity around 8% among adolescents thought, other studies in the same metropolitan area reported much higher members. Differences were attributed to age groups studied and urban vs suburban dynamics.

Akinyemi (2020) observed that adolescents from polygamous families or single-parent households showed higher tendencies to engage in early sexual activity, presumably due to less supervision or family discord. Low socioeconomic status and poverty emerged as motivators for early or transactional sex, especially among girls seeking material gain or facing economic constraints. Oburu (2021) stressed that in Rivers State, current sex education efforts are limited and inconsistent. Traditional and religious values may impede open discussion of sexuality, yet the pressing realities of early sexual behavior and health risks demand culturally sensitive, relevant educational interventions. Encourage parental involvement and community leaders to support sexuality education that respects local values while promoting safe practices.

CONCLUSION

It is very important to put into consideration acts capable of denting one's name in school whether teacher or students. Immoral behaviour is rampard in secondary schools, mostly the public schools. This is due to lack of co-ordination, supervision, absence of counseling unit, inability to manage large crowd in school etc. teachers and school administrators should ensure discipline, reward for good behaviour, periodic counseling and parent's participation in school management. The school as a matter of urgency should put to use guidance counselors, lecturers, to improve moral standard of their schools and students. The use of Android phones should be prohibited or put on strict check among the junior & secondary school students. Parents should be made to sign undertaken against their buying android phones for their ward and control what they watch at home on televisions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. There is need to involve local educators and cultural stakeholders in designing the curriculum to ensure acceptance and community support.
2. To develop comprehensive sex education programmes that respect local cultural and religious values while providing accurate information about sexual health, relationships, consent, and reproductive rights.
3. Encourage families to serve as the first point of education on sexual morality, boundaries, and self-respect.
4. Train youth leaders to challenges harmful norms like gender stereotypes or stigma around contraception while promoting respectful behavior and informed decision making.
5. Encourage the Rivers State Ministry of Education to adopt formal policies on adolescent sexual health education that align with cultural realities but prioritize safety and well-being.

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